

Speculation on the Notion of Probability in 2-Slit Interference

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In classical physics, probability seems to be associated with a loss of knowledge rather than the creation of a new physical state. For example, if a coin is heads, there are two physical states possible, heads up and tails, and one knows for certain one has heads initially. When the coin is tossed, a new state is not created, but one simply loses information about the state of the coin.

For a quantum free particle, E and p are certain, but there are probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ associated with t and x which are not manifest and so one might suggest there is no entropy. If an impulse hit occurs on a large target, the uncertainties in t and x are probably not manifest and one considers only the effects based on p . On the other hand, if there are two slits about \hbar/p apart, a new physical state, namely an entangled state $\exp(ipr_1) + \exp(ipr_2)$, is created based on the interaction. The particle goes through one slit or the other (with equal probability), but this has no effect on the interference pattern. This is a second probability in the problem. Like with $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-iEt)$ for a free particle, the interference pattern is based on the particle interacting with both slits regardless of the one through which it passes.

Nevertheless, there is a probability associated with the slit through which the particle passes and this may become associated with a new measurement, like the manner in which $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle becomes linked with 2-slit interference. Specifically, this new measurement is one in which a detector is placed behind each slit. The probability associated with the slit through which the particle passes determines which detector is activated. A new quantum state, namely a slit 1 or slit 2 state is created because these are the states allowed by quantum mechanics. In other words, the probability is associated with the slit through which the particle passes and not with the entangled state $\exp(ipr_1) + \exp(ipr_2)$. The probability in the problem lies with the slit through which the particle passes and this is irrelevant unless there is new measurement, i.e. detectors at each slit (after the particle passes through). In such a case, the slit probability becomes associated with these detectors. As a result, we argue one does not really have a collapse of the entangled state into a slit one or slit state, but rather the slit 1 and slit 2 states are associated with the probability for the particle to pass through one slit or the other and get created by the interaction with the detector. This is a trajectory probability while the entangled state is based on interaction, i.e. the particle interacting with both slits regardless through which slit the particle passes.

Classical Probability

Classical probability is associated, it seems, with a loss of information. If a coin or die is in a certain state (heads up or 3), one knows a priori the possible states and in addition, the state in which the coin or die sits. A toss or roll causes one to lose information about the state, but does not lead to the creation of a new physical state. As a result, if person A tosses a coin and loses information, person B may actually know the state of the coin by performing a measurement which does not affect the state. Person A does not have this knowledge because he/she did not perform the measurement.

We argue that this type of classical probability is still present in 2-slit interference, but further features occur as there are two considerations: A the trajectory of the particle and B the interaction of the particle. In classical physics, these occur at the same place while in quantum mechanics they do not, we argue. Thus, in quantum mechanics one must consider both features and this leads to results which are different from classical physics.

Two Slit Interference

If one considers a quantum free particle with certain energy E , p , then it still has uncertainty or probability associated with x, t given by $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-iEt)$. If the particle moves freely in space, then these probabilities are not manifested and it is as if they are not there. One might argue for the entropy being zero. Furthermore, if the particle strikes a large target or moves towards a 2-slit apparatus with slit widths $\gg \hbar/p$ and slit separation $\gg \hbar/p$, one again has a classical situation. In order to see the effects of $\exp(ipx)$ one requires an interaction which reveals them.

In particular, a 2-slit apparatus with slit separations and widths of the order of \hbar/p allows the particle to interact with both slits regardless through which slit it passes. There seem to be two considerations. The first deals with an interaction and leads to the creation of a single entangled state which involves both slits, $\exp(ipr_1) + \exp(ipr_2)$, where r_1 and r_2 are lengths from each slit to the same point on a screen far away. This entangled state is associated with probability, namely that for the particle to arrive at different points on a screen far away, but no information about the slit through which the particle passes is needed for this pattern. This is a separate probability which is not manifested, just like $\exp(ipx)$ is not manifested for free travel in empty space or the striking of a large target etc.

The probability of passing through slit 1 or slit 2, however, can be associated with a measurement. In particular, one may place a detector behind slit 1 and another behind slit 2. In this case, a particle passing through slit 1 hits detector 1 and through slit 2, detector 2. This measurement is associated strictly with the slit probability and breaks the entangled state creating either a slit 1 or slit 2 state and so interference disappears. Traditionally, it seems that one considers this an example of wavefunction collapse, but we argue that in fact two different sets of probabilities are present. The entangled state is due to the probability $\exp(ipx)$ and means the particle interacts with both slits. Its trajectory (passing through one slit or the other) is irrelevant to the interference pattern (one kind of probability measurement). The entangled state, however, is automatically associated with a second probability, namely the probability through which slit the particle passes. This may be linked with a separate measurement associated with this particular probability, namely placing detectors behind each slit. We stress that one should consider $\exp(ipx)$ and the slit probabilities separately when analyzing 2-slit interference because the 2-slit interaction is linked with $\exp(ipx)$ while the detector measurements, with slit probability.

As a result, we suggest linking specific probabilities to specific measurements instead of considering the entangled state directly with the slit 1 and slit 2 states and treating slit probabilities as the only probabilities in the problem. We note that the slit probability is a classical type of probability, while $\exp(ipx)$ is not. The latter leads to entangled (i.e. new states).

Similarity with Sz Eigenstates

It seems that there may be an analogy with spin projection states (e.g. spin \uparrow). One may have a pure state (spin up or down) along one axis, e.g. z, but an entangled state along the x or y axis. One may note that completely different measurements are associated with finding the spin projection along each axis.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that one must be careful when considering the various probabilities present in a problem. We suggest that a coin toss or die roll involves one kind of probability, a loss of information, but no new physical state is created.

A quantum free particle with certain E, p has associated probabilities $\exp(-iEt), \exp(ipx)$, but these do not manifest themselves in free space and so it is as if they are not present. A 2-slit apparatus with slit widths and spacings of the order of \hbar/p , however, allows $\exp(ipx)$ to reveal itself in that the particle interacts with both slits creating an entangled state. This is a new physical state, not a lack of information about the slit through which the particle passes. It leads to a probabilistic distribution on a screen far away from the slits. There is, however, also a classical probability associated with the slit through which the particle passes, but it is not relevant for the interference probability result, just as $\exp(ipx)$ is not relevant for motion in free space or strikes against a large target.

One may, however, perform a measurement linked with the slit probability. In particular, if one places a detector behind each slit, then if the particle passes through slit 1, it strikes detector 1 and through slit 2, detector 2. In such a case, one creates states associated with slit 1 or slit 2 as these are the possible quantum states that can result from these detectors. These are based on the slit probability. As a result, we prefer not to consider 2-slit interference with slit detectors in terms of a collapse of the entangled wavefunction. The entangled wavefunction is a new physical state associated with $\exp(ipx)$ and is created by interactions with both slits. The slit 1 or slit 2 wavefunction is based on slit probability and created by the detectors. We argue that this is similar to the idea of measuring the z component of spin. A pure state along one axis is an entangled state along another.